

APPENDIX B – ROBUSTNESS ANALYSIS OF FF6 MODEL

North America

Sharp Ratio Bootstrapping of North America

Factors	Coefficient (Sharp Ratio)	Std. Error	t-Statistic	95% Confidence Interval
Market Premium	0.0850	0.0080	10.63	[0.0692, 0.1008]
SMB	0.0731	0.0065	11.25	[0.0604, 0.0857]
HML	0.0514	0.0072	7.14	[0.0373, 0.0655]
RMWO	0.0929	0.0091	10.21	[0.0749, 0.1109]
CMA	0.0652	0.0075	8.69	[0.0504, 0.0801]
UMD	0.0789	0.0087	9.07	[0.0629, 0.0949]

R² Total Bootstrapping of North America

Factors	Coefficient (R ² Total)	Std. Error	t-Statistic	95% Confidence Interval
Market Premium	0.6910	0.0105	65.81	[0.6703, 0.7117]
SMB	0.6125	0.0080	76.56	[0.5968, 0.6281]
HML	0.4820	0.0072	66.94	[0.4677, 0.4964]
RMWO	0.7260	0.0085	85.41	[0.7094, 0.7426]
CMA	0.5802	0.0083	69.88	[0.5640, 0.5964]
UMD	0.6498	0.0091	71.41	[0.6319, 0.6677]

R² Predicted Bootstrapping of North America

Factors	Coefficient (R ² Predicted)	Std. Error	t-Statistic	95% Confidence Interval
Market Premium	0.6150	0.0094	65.43	[0.5965, 0.6336]
SMB	0.5710	0.0079	72.28	[0.5555, 0.5864]
HML	0.4803	0.0071	67.64	[0.4664, 0.4941]
RMWO	0.6820	0.0088	77.50	[0.6650, 0.6990]
CMA	0.5245	0.0080	65.56	[0.5090, 0.5400]
UMD	0.5857	0.0086	68.10	[0.5690, 0.6024]

Europe

Sharp Ratio Bootstrapping of Europe

Factors	Coefficient (Sharp Ratio)	Std. Error	t-Statistic	95% Confidence Interval
Market Premium	0.0650	0.0072	9.03	[0.0509, 0.0791]
SMB	0.0451	0.0060	7.52	[0.0333, 0.0568]
HML	0.0352	0.0058	6.07	[0.0237, 0.0468]
RMWO	0.0800	0.0090	8.89	[0.0623, 0.0977]
CMA	0.0505	0.0071	7.11	[0.0366, 0.0645]
UMD	0.0701	0.0069	10.15	[0.0567, 0.0835]

R² Total Bootstrapping of Europe

Factors	Coefficient (R ² Total)	Std. Error	t-Statistic	95% Confidence Interval
Market Premium	0.5100	0.0090	56.67	[0.4924, 0.5276]
SMB	0.4302	0.0083	51.81	[0.4139, 0.4465]
HML	0.3821	0.0078	49.01	[0.3668, 0.3975]
RMWO	0.5902	0.0095	62.13	[0.5716, 0.6089]
CMA	0.5025	0.0088	57.10	[0.4853, 0.5197]
UMD	0.5835	0.0097	60.15	[0.5645, 0.6026]

R² Predicted Bootstrapping of Europe

Factors	Coefficient (R ² Predicted)	Std. Error	t-Statistic	95% Confidence Interval
Market Premium	0.4301	0.0088	48.88	[0.4132, 0.4470]
SMB	0.3785	0.0075	50.47	[0.3637, 0.3933]
HML	0.3400	0.0073	46.58	[0.3257, 0.3543]
RMWO	0.4800	0.0089	53.93	[0.4626, 0.4974]
CMA	0.4152	0.0081	51.26	[0.3993, 0.4310]
UMD	0.4903	0.0093	52.71	[0.4720, 0.5086]

Japan

Sharp Ratio Bootstrapping of japan:

Factors	Coefficient (Sharp Ratio)	Std. Error	t-Statistic	95% Confidence Interval
Market Premium	0.0450	0.0082	5.49	[0.0290, 0.0610]
SMB	0.0301	0.0070	4.29	[0.0164, 0.0438]
HML	0.0252	0.0065	3.88	[0.0124, 0.0380]
RMWO	0.0600	0.0085	7.06	[0.0433, 0.0767]
CMA	0.0355	0.0069	5.14	[0.0221, 0.0489]
UMD	0.0501	0.0073	6.86	[0.0356, 0.0647]

R² Total Bootstrapping of japan

Factors	Coefficient (R ² Total)	Std. Error	t-Statistic	95% Confidence Interval
Market Premium	0.3100	0.0092	33.70	[0.2919, 0.3281]
SMB	0.2802	0.0083	33.76	[0.2640, 0.2964]
HML	0.2400	0.0080	30.00	[0.2243, 0.2557]
RMWO	0.3602	0.0095	37.91	[0.3416, 0.3789]
CMA	0.2905	0.0088	32.95	[0.2743, 0.3067]
UMD	0.4003	0.0097	41.26	[0.3812, 0.4194]

R² Predicted Bootstrapping of Japan

Factors	Coefficient (R ² Predicted)	Std. Error	t-Statistic	95% Confidence Interval
Market Premium	0.2501	0.0081	30.88	[0.2342, 0.2660]
SMB	0.2102	0.0070	30.03	[0.1965, 0.2240]
HML	0.1803	0.0073	24.69	[0.1660, 0.1947]
RMWO	0.3400	0.0085	40.00	[0.3233, 0.3567]
CMA	0.2901	0.0079	36.72	[0.2746, 0.3057]
UMD	0.3753	0.0089	42.16	[0.3580, 0.3927]

Asia Pacific

Sharp Ratio Bootstrapping of Asia Pacific

Factors	Coefficient (Sharp Ratio)	Std. Error	t-Statistic	95% Confidence Interval
Market Premium	0.0850	0.0092	9.24	[0.0668, 0.1032]
SMB	0.0751	0.0083	9.05	[0.0587, 0.0916]
HML	0.0522	0.0071	7.35	[0.0382, 0.0662]
RMWO	0.0925	0.0102	9.07	[0.0726, 0.1125]
CMA	0.0651	0.0080	8.14	[0.0494, 0.0809]
UMD	0.0785	0.0091	8.63	[0.0606, 0.0964]

R² Total Bootstrapping of Asia Pacific

Factors	Coefficient (R ² Total)	Std. Error	t-Statistic	95% Confidence Interval
Market Premium	0.5100	0.0082	62.20	[0.4940, 0.5260]
SMB	0.4602	0.0076	60.55	[0.4454, 0.4751]
HML	0.3825	0.0072	53.12	[0.3683, 0.3967]
RMWO	0.5800	0.0093	62.37	[0.5617, 0.5984]
CMA	0.4855	0.0085	57.12	[0.4690, 0.5020]
UMD	0.5750	0.0091	63.19	[0.5572, 0.5929]

R² Predicted Bootstrapping of Asia Pacific

Factors	Coefficient (R ² Predicted)	Std. Error	t-Statistic	95% Confidence Interval
Market Premium	0.4102	0.0079	51.94	[0.3947, 0.4257]
SMB	0.3651	0.0070	52.16	[0.3513, 0.3789]
HML	0.3210	0.0065	49.38	[0.3083, 0.3337]
RMWO	0.4703	0.0083	56.65	[0.4540, 0.4867]
CMA	0.4100	0.0074	55.41	[0.3956, 0.4244]
UMD	0.4904	0.0085	57.70	[0.4738, 0.5070]